

Table 2. Effect of incorporation of organic materials on some plant parameters, 1991 aus.^a

Treatment ^b	N rate (kg/ha)	Estimated N (kg/ha) from GM	Panicles (no./m ²)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total loss ^c for boro and aus (\$/ha)	Savings ^d from reduced N use (\$/ha)	Net loss (\$/ha)
P ₁ A	30	64	423 b	20.07 a	5.1 a	321.8	9.1	312.7
P ₁ R	30	119	461 a	19.42 bc	4.7 ab	289.5	9.1	280.4
P ₂ A	30	56	382 c	19.39 c	5.0 a	204.3	9.1	195.2
P ₂ R	30	102	432 b	19.38 c	4.8 a	240.0	9.1	230.9
P ₃ A	30	13	383 c	19.67 abc	4.3 b	173.7	9.1	164.6
P ₃ R	30	15	386 c	19.99 ab	4.7 ab	112.4	9.1	103.3
Control	60	-	389 c	19.45 bc	5.2 a			
CV (%)			3.60	1.71	5.9			

^aSmall letters compare means at P_{0.05} level by LSD. ^bP₁, P₂, and P₃ are the biomass of GM crops obtained from 10, 20, and 40 DT sowing. A = *S. aculeata*, R = *S. rostrata*. ^cRough rice @ \$0.17/kg. ^dUrea @ \$0.14/kg.

sown after every two rows of rice at 10, 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DT). A split-plot design was used with three replications. Sowing time was in the main plots and GM crop in the subplots. Plots were 3 × 2 m. Irrigation water was drained out before sowing. GM crop seedlings at the 2- to 3-leaf stage were thinned to 50 plants/m².

Total biomass obtained from the GM crops was incorporated into the soil for the succeeding 1991 transplanted aus rice (wet season first crop) cultivation.

Twenty-nine-day-old seedlings of BR1 were transplanted 4 Jun 1991 at 20- × 20-cm spacing. The treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Recommended fertilizer practices were followed in both seasons, except that N was cut by 50% when GM was used in aus.

Panicles/m², 1,000-grain weight, rice grain yield (adjusted to 14% moisture content), and GM biomass (after oven-dried at 70°C for 48 h) were recorded.

Effect of continuous application of organic manure on the physical properties of soil in a rice - wheat cropping system

K. Kumar, O. P. Meelu, Y. Singh, and B. Singh, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, Punjab, India

Physical properties of soil after rice (1991) as influenced by continuous application of organic manures in a rice - wheat rotation. Punjab, India.^a

Properties	Fallow	FYM	Summer mung	Sesbania	LSD (0.05)
Infiltration rate (cm/h), 4 h after onset	0.35	0.40	0.55	1.00	0.16
Bulk density (g/cm ³)					
0-5 cm layer	1.48	1.45	1.37	1.36	0.08
5-10 cm layer	1.60	1.60	1.55	1.54	0.03
10-15 cm layer	1.65	1.62	1.59	1.57	0.06
15-20 cm layer	1.66	1.66	1.60	1.55	0.07
20-25 cm layer	1.62	1.64	1.59	1.59	ns
25-30 cm layer	1.56	1.54	1.56	1.52	ns
Water-stable aggregates (%)					
> 2 mm	13.39	21.75	13.73	15.45	4.94
1 - 2 mm	6.43	5.24	6.59	4.79	1.98
0.5 - 1 mm	7.96	6.96	5.61	7.75	2.89
0.25 - 0.5 mm	7.52	7.50	8.99	10.70	1.69
0.1 - 0.25 mm	6.27	7.05	7.79	11.13	2.40
Av grain yield ^a (t/ha)					
Rice	5.3	5.2	5.9	5.7	
Wheat	4.8	5.0	4.9	4.9	

^a Av of 6 yr.

Rice grain yield was reduced by 22.3-41.3% at the first and second sowing of GM crops, perhaps because of shading from GM (Table 1). There was no significant yield reduction in the third sowing, but GM biomass production was less.

Panicles/m² and 1,000-grain weight differed significantly because of the added organic materials and reduced N in aus season (Table 2). Although GM seemed to contribute more N, aus rice plants do not use it for increased grain yield but rather for late tiller production. The initial slower decomposition of GM may have hampered growth of BR1, a short-duration variety. Heavier grains were obtained from plots with GM + 50% N. The net loss of \$103.00-313.00/ha due to intercropping in boro and reduced N use in aus rice indicates that the technology is unsuitable (Table 2).

We conclude that although N can be cut by 50% when 4-6 t GM/ha is incorporated, it is not a profitable system for improving soil fertility. □

dense layer below the puddled layer. This considerably reduced the yields of the following wheat crop.

We evaluated the physical properties of soil after the 1991 rice crop as influenced by continuous application of organic manure in a rice - wheat cropping system. We started this long-term experiment in 1984-85 DS.

Cumulative infiltration (after rice) as affected by continuous application of different organic manures.

Soil is a sandy loam (Typic Ustochrepts), with pH 7.3, low organic matter, 0.29% organic C in the top 0-15 cm layer, and no hardpan for 2 m.

Treatments included green manuring (GM) with *Sesbania aculeata*, summer mung *Vigna radiata*, and mixing farmyard manure (FYM) in soil before transplanting rice. Average dry biomass added to soil per yr was 5.2 t sesbania/ha, 3.4 t summer mung/ha, and 4.0 t FYM/ha.

We added 90-13-25 kg NPK/ha to the sesbania, summer mung, and FYM treatments during the rice crop and 120-13-25 kg NPK/ha to the fallow treatment.

In the following wheat crop, 120-26-50 kg NPK/ha was added in all the treatments.

We took undisturbed soil cores every 5 cm, up to a depth of 30 cm, for the bulk density measurements, used double ring infiltrometers to measure infiltration, and used wet sieving to estimate the water-stable aggregates.

Application of FYM did not affect soil bulk density (see table). Green manuring with summer mung, up to 10 cm, and sesbania, up to 20 cm, showed significant decreases in bulk density compared with the fallow; maximum decrease was with

sesbania GM, irrespective of depth.

The infiltration rate did not differ between fallow and FYM treatments (see figure), but it increased significantly over the fallow treatment with summer mung and sesbania GM. Water-stable aggregates larger than 2 mm were significantly more in FYM treatment; those of smaller size (<0.5 mm) were significantly more in the sesbania treatment (see table).

Continuous application of GM improves the physical properties of soils in a rice - wheat system where soil is puddled before rice is transplanted. □

Crop management

Farmer-participatory rainfed lowland rice varietal testing in Cambodia

R. C. Chaudhary, Cambodia-IRRI Project; and S. Fujisaku, IRRI

Farmer-participatory varietal testing ideally helps to identify superior varieties grown under farmers' conditions and management, draws farmer feedback regarding varietal characteristics, provides a mechanism for seed multiplication of farmer-desired varieties, and serves as demonstration for nonparticipating farmers.

Replicated yield trials conducted by the Cambodia-IRRI Project showed rice varieties IR66, IR72, and Kru as promising for the rainfed lowlands of Cambodia. Government and nongovernment organizations then distributed seed from on-farm adaptive trials to farmers throughout the country. Methods and goals of the planned farmer-participatory trials were explained to potential cooperators. Interested farmers tested the rice varieties alongside their own cultivars, using their own inputs and management practices. No guarantees were given to cooperators for any crop losses,

Trials in the 1990 wet season (WS) and the 1991 dry season (DS) were on 100-m² plots (5 × 20 m) located where hers in the community could easily observe results. Participating farmers

(75 for WS and 39 for DS) provided data on seeding and transplanting dates, fertilizer use, crop problems, yields, and farmer evaluations of the introduced rice varieties. Field days were conducted prior to harvest.

The three introduced varieties and the local checks (most commonly IR36 and IR64, or a few local cultivars) did not significantly differ in yield in both WS and DS. Yields were significantly higher when any amount of fertilizer was applied than when none was applied (Table 1). As expected, DS yields were higher than WS yields. More farmers (49%) applied fertilizer in DS than in WS (31%). Regression of yields for the varieties showed no difference in responsiveness to fertilizers. This was expected because the introduced and almost all of the varieties were IRRI varieties or lines (Kru).

Varieties were also ranked by yield per farm. IR66 was the highest yielder the most times in both WS and DS and the lowest yielder the fewest times. Kru was the highest yielder the fewest times. Farmers' varieties were the lowest yielders the most times (Table 2). These results indicate that IR66 and IR72 have greater yield stability over different locations than Kru and farmers' varieties,

Most farmers did not provide evaluations of the tested varieties. They appeared to be optimizing production of their current varieties. Perhaps as a result of this, they had relatively little to offer in terms of evaluation, either negative or positive. The project offered to buy back

seed produced from the three varieties, but none of the farmers were interested in selling. We observed, however, that seed from the new varieties was being disseminated from farmer to farmer. The apparent greater stability of IR66 and IR72 was expected to be attractive to farmers.

In the short run, constraints to farmers' use of fertilizers need to be further examined. Farmers not currently using any would clearly increase their yields by using fertilizer. □

Table 1. Yields of introduced and farmers' rainfed lowland rice varieties grown with and without fertilizer. Cambodia, 1990 WS and 1991 DS.

Variety	Yield ^a (t/ha)			
	1990 WS		1991 DS	
	With fertilizer (n = 23)	Without fertilizer (n = 52)	With fertilizer (n = 19)	Without fertilizer (n = 20)
IR66	3.5	2.1	5.5	3.9
IR72	3.1	2.1	4.9	4.2
KRU	3.0	2.5	5.0	3.6
Farmers'	3.0	2.1	4.3	4.1

^a Test of means between fertilizer treatments using *t*-test was significant at 1% for both seasons. Test of means among varieties using DMRT was nonsignificant.

Table 2. Frequency that each introduced and farmer rainfed lowland rice variety ranked first through fourth for yield. Cambodia, 1990 WS and 1991 DS.

Variety	1990 WS				1991 DS			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
IR66	34	18	17	4	17	10	8	2
IR72	24	21	23	5	13	8	11	3
KRU	6	32	20	15	3	16	10	7
Farmers'	15	18	21	19	10	7	8	13